

2nd Evaluation Exercise on Micro Frontends

Provide your personal information and answer the questions on the following pages about the Nab-bank application.

What is your full name?

In this exercise, you will need to access two documents:

- Description of the proposed architecture to implement the application using Micro Frontends
- Website with the anti-patterns catalog for Micro Frontends

Access the Nab-bank architecture description.

I was able to access the architecture description

Access the Micro Frontends anti-patterns catalog.

I was able to access the catalog

Architectural Inspection

Consider that you are a Junior Developer who is about to start working at Nab-bank. You have just learned more about the system's architecture, and you have been asked to analyze the MFE-based architecture:

Would you model the system using Micro Frontends differently? Would you keep the same MFEs, create new ones, or modify the existing ones? Also consider the screens and fragments.

Did you identify any anti-patterns in the architecture? If so, which ones?

Evolution and Bug Fixes

Answer how you would solve the task below, assuming you are a developer working at Nab-bank. Feel free to propose new MFEs, shared libraries, screens and/or fragments, in addition to modifying existing ones.

Note: consider the architecture described in the PDF document without including the changes proposed by you in the architectural inspection.

Suppose that `mfe-loan` is updated and now the **Loan Section fragment** has a new required parameter: the current account balance of the user. The `mfe-loan` is deployed (sent to production), and the home screen of the app, which imports this fragment in the `mfe-home`, starts showing an error because it was not updated to pass the new parameter to the fragment.

Loan Section Fragment

What would you do to ensure that deploying `mfe-loan` does not cause an error in `home`, allowing the screen code to be adjusted later, gradually and safely?

Did you use any anti-pattern to answer this question? If so, state its name and how it helped.

Evolution and Bug Fixes

Answer how you would solve the task below considering that you are a developer working at Nab-bank. Feel free to propose new MFEs, shared libraries, screens and/or fragments, as well as modify existing ones.

Note: consider the architecture described in the PDF document without taking into account the changes you proposed in the architectural inspection.

Consider the following order of communications between `mfe-digital-account`, `mfe-loan`, and `mfe-home`:

- After successfully completing a PIX transfer, `mfe-digital-account` calls a function received as a parameter from `mfe-home` to update the account balance shown on the home screen.
- `mfe-home` updates the account balance and changes the parameter passed to the loan section fragment from `mfe-loan`.
- `mfe-loan` then reprocesses and recalculates the loan offer based on the user's current balance.

Currently, there is difficulty in updating this flow because a change may impact the communication between all fragments. How would you increase the independence between the MFEs while maintaining communication between them?

Did you use any anti-pattern to answer this question? If so, state its name and how it helped.

Evolution and Bug Fixes

Answer how you would solve the task below considering you are a developer working at Nab-bank. Feel free to propose new MFEs, shared libraries, screens and/or fragments, in addition to modifying existing ones.

Note: consider the architecture described in the PDF document without including the changes you proposed during the architectural inspection.

Suppose that every time you make a change in `mfe-cards`, it is necessary to access the server where the application is deployed and manually upload the code changes. Note that the deployment could be performed with an automatic command sequence. How would you ensure that code deployment is no longer manual?

Did you use any anti-pattern to answer this question? If so, indicate its name and how it helped.

Evolution and bug fixing

Answer how you would solve the task below considering you are a developer

working at Nab-bank. Feel free to propose new MFEs, shared libraries, screens and/or fragments, as well as modify existing ones.

Note: consider the architecture described in the PDF document, without including the changes you proposed in the architectural inspection.

Suppose that the app's home screen implemented in `mfe-home` is showing an error that is not related to any component implemented directly on the page, indicating that it may originate from one of the screen's fragments. What would you do to prevent an error in a fragment from making the entire screen unavailable?

Did you use any anti-pattern to answer this question? If so, mention its name and explain how it helped.

Evolution and bug fixing

Answer how you would solve the task below considering you are a developer working at Nab-bank. Feel free to propose new MFEs, shared libraries, screens and/or fragments, as well as modify existing ones.

Note: consider the architecture described in the PDF document, excluding any changes you may have proposed during the architectural inspection.

Suppose that `mfe-investment` is being treated as the module responsible for offering various investment products. It started as a module exclusively for CDB (a fixed-income investment product) and was later adjusted to also support investments in Government Bonds (Tesouro Direto). Now, Nab-bank wants to implement a new investment product that works very differently from both CDB and Government Bonds — it has specific screens and a distinct purchase flow. This implementation poses a challenge because the `mfe-investment` code is tightly coupled to how CDB and Government Bonds work, making it hard to add a new product.

What would you have done during the development of the CDB and Government Bonds features to make `mfe-investment` more generic and facilitate the implementation of new investment products?

Did you use any anti-pattern to answer this question? If so, mention its name and explain how it helped.

Evolution and bug fixing

Answer how you would solve the task below considering you are a developer working at Nab-bank. Feel free to propose new MFEs, shared libraries, screens and/or fragments, as well as modify existing ones.

Note: consider the architecture described in the PDF document, excluding any changes you may have proposed during the architectural inspection.

Nab-bank is launching a new investment format called NuCoin — a proprietary currency within the app that users accumulate by making credit card purchases. This feature consists of several screens and fragments, some of which are shown below:

Main screen

NuCoins Statement Screen

Prize draw details

Benefit Screen

What architectural changes are necessary for the development of the components above?

Did you use any anti-pattern to answer this question? If so, mention its name and explain how it helped.

Evolution and bug fixing

Answer how you would solve the task below considering you are a developer working at Nab-bank. Feel free to propose new MFEs, shared libraries, screens and/or fragments, as well as modify existing ones.

Note: consider the architecture described in the PDF document, excluding any changes you may have proposed during the architectural inspection.

Nab-bank is launching a new feature called “Charge Everything to Credit”, which allows PIX transfers and boleto (bank slip) payments to be made using a credit card. Additionally, one-time credit card purchases can also be converted into installments. This feature includes the following visual components:

Choose what to use credit for

Screen that displays one-time purchases that can be converted into installments

Fragment with the option to split a PIX payment into installments

What architectural changes are necessary for the development of the components above?

Did you use any anti-pattern to answer this question? If so, mention its name and explain how it helped.

Evolution and bug fixing

Answer how you would solve the task below considering you are a developer working at Nab-bank. Feel free to propose new MFEs, shared libraries, screens and/or fragments, as well as modify existing ones.

Note: consider the architecture described in the PDF document, excluding any changes you may have proposed during the architectural inspection.

Suppose you have just finished implementing a new MFE and now need to deploy it and integrate it with other MFEs already in production. You encounter many difficulties in this process and realize these are recurring problems. How could you speed up the deployment of a new MFE next time?

Did you use any anti-pattern to answer this question? If so, mention its name and explain how it helped.

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To finish, please answer the question below (it will not impact your grade, so feel free to respond honestly).

Rate your perceived knowledge of Micro Frontends on a scale from 0 to 5 (decimal numbers allowed):

BEFORE LEAVING THE LAB, please fill out the feedback form about the anti-patterns catalog.

I have already responded or WILL respond to the feedback form NOW.